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Avalokiteśvara of the Six Syllables: Locating the Practice of the “Great Vehicle” in the Landscape of Central India*

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The long-standing characterization of Buddhism as a religion in decline after the Gupta period is known to be fraught with inaccuracy. While there can be little doubt that the increasing influence of Śaivism from the sixth century C.E. had a significant impact on the religious life of northern India as a whole, the ongoing vitality of Buddhism is well attested in eastern India where Nālandā developed into a powerful monastic institution with trans-national networks across Asia (see, for example, Sanderson 2009; Bronkhorst 2012; Willis 2013). In addition to the rising tide of theistic Hinduism in both its popular and esoteric forms, the decline of Buddhism is sometimes attributed to its retreat into large monasteries, a development which resulted in the faith losing touch with the population at large and so with its sources of patronage. These propositions, based on a series of armchair assumptions, fall down before an examination of archaeological sites and sculptural remains, as Abhishek Amar’s recent studies in the Bodhgayā region have shown (Amar 2012). Outside Bihar, similar conclusions can be reached in central India where Buddhism continued to flourish at monastic centers, most notably at Sānchī. A significant later addition at Sānchī is Temple 45. This building, dating to the last years of the ninth century C.E., contains one of the largest surviving Buddha images in India (fig. 1; Willis 2000: no. 7). Sānchī was dominated by the Hemavata school, at least until about the eighth century C.E., so it can be regarded as a predominantly Theravāda place, problematic as that term has recently become (Willis 2001; Gethin 2012: 1–63). Certainly the fact that the main *caitya* was

not replaced or overshadowed by a temple, as happened at Bodhgayā and Sārnāth, and that when the temple was built at Sānchī it was relegated to the edge of the site, shows that a conservative cult predominated there. Although some inscriptions hint at a Mahāyāna presence at Sānchī (Tsukamoto 1996: nos. 915, 917), it is images from other places in central India, such as Khajurāho, Mahoba, Unao and Bilhari, that are indicative of later and more mature trends within Buddhism (see for example Desai 1996; Dikshit 1921; Willis 1996: 122). Among these is a large seated Avalokiteśvara from Gyāraspur that awaits systematic study. It belongs to the eleventh century and is now in the museum at Bhopāl.

The ways in which followers of Mahāyāna established themselves in the countryside around Sānchī is shown by a cave in one of the ridges near Raisen, about ten kilometers from Sānchī. The ridge in question is located to the north of Raisen town and is remarkable for the large natural pond on the hilltop that never goes dry, even in the summer. At the brow of the hill is a natural cavern, once the source of a spring. Around this cavern are rock-cut images of the Buddha and Tārā (figs. 2–3). The relief sculptures can be dated to the eleventh century. These are the only rock-cut Buddhist images in the region; they have not been published previously.

Among the finds in one of the caves at this site is a seated Buddha inscribed with the *Pratītyasamutpādagāthā* and a request that this meritorious gift (*deyadharmā*) be for the welfare of all living beings (fig. 4). Given the potential interest of this record I asked my colleague

Fig. 1. Drawing of the seated Buddha in Sanchī temple 45 (Madhya Pradesh, India) by John Henry Bagnold in 1818-1819. Royal Asiatic Society 07.006.

Fig. 2. Cave shrine in the ridge north of Raisen (Madhya Pradesh, India) with rock-cut images of the Buddha and Tārā. Photo: M. Willis.

Fig 3. Rock-cut image of Tārā at the cave-shrine north of Raisen (Madhya Pradesh, India), 11th c. Photo: M. Willis.

Fig. 4. Inscribed pedestal of a seated Buddha in the cave shrine north of Raisen (Madhya Pradesh, India), 11th c. Photo: M. Willis.

Dániel Balogh to see if he could make sense of it in view of his expert knowledge of Paramāra paleography. He very kindly supplied the following reading.¹ Discussion of the formulae used in this record can be found in Cousins 2003 and Schopen 2005: 244.

Text

1. siddham² || ye dha(r)mmā he{tu}prabhavā
hetun te(s)ān tathāgato (h)y avāda
2. n teṣā(m) ca yo nirodha e(vaṃvā){dī}
(ma)hāśra(va)ṇaḥ || deya{dha}
3. (r)mmo yaṃ pravaramahāyānayāyi(na)ḥ
param(opā)saka
4. vāttam³kasya yad a[tra] pu(ṇ)yaṃ tad
bhava(t)v (a)cā(r)yopādhyāyamā
5. tāp(i)t(ṛ)pūrvva(ṇ){ga}maṃ (kṛ)tvā saka[la]
satvārās(e)r anu
6. {ttarajñānapha}{lāvā}{pta}{ma?} i{t}i ||

Emended Text

1. siddham || ye dharmmā hetuprabhavā hetun
teṣān tathāgato hy avada

2. t teṣāṃ ca yo nirodha evamvādī
mahāśramaṇaḥ || deyadha
3. rmmo yaṃ pravaramahāyānayāyinaḥ paramo-
pāsaka
4. vaṭṭāṅkasya || yad atra puṇyaṃ tad bhavtv
ācāryyopādhyāyamā
5. tāpitrpūrvvaṅgamam kṛtvā sakalasetvarāser
anu
6. ttarajñānaphalāvāptaya iti ||

Translation

Success! Those *dharm*-s that arise from a cause, the Tathāgata has declared their cause, and that which is the cessation of them. Thus the great renunciant has taught. This is the worthy gift of Vaṭṭāṅka (?), a devoted *upāsaka* among the followers of the most excellent Mahāyāna. Whatever merit there is (in this gift), may it be for the attainment of the fruit of supreme knowledge by all the multitude of living beings, having placed first my preceptors, teachers and parents.

Although the inscription does not name a king or give a date, it is important nonetheless from

Fig. 5. Seated Śaḍakṣarī Avalokiteśvara (Madhya Pradesh, India), 11th c. British Museum Asia 1967,0213.1.

the religious point of view. Its importance lies in the fact that it explicitly mentions that a lay follower of Mahāyāna donated the image. With the rock-cut sculptures just mentioned, this shows that the cave-shrine at Raisen was developed by followers of Mahāyāna and thus that Mahāyāna operated concurrently with Theravāda in the eleventh century, albeit at one remove from the most important and oldest centers. While some finds at Sānchī belonging to the post-Gupta period suggest that Mahāyāna enjoyed a presence there, as just noted, the Raisen finds demonstrate nonetheless that Mahāyāna had its own holy places and a community large enough to sponsor votive images.

The antiquity of this community is uncertain. Given the archaeological traces found so far, it appears that Mahāyāna may have been present in Sānchī from the early centuries C.E., as attested by a Kuṣāṇa-period head showing a Bodhisattva with a seated Buddha in the turban (Hamid et al. 1922: 38) and an inscription on the base of a Bodhisattva image (Willis 1999–2000: 269–73). However, the corpus of imagery as a whole suggests that a second wave of Mahāyāna arrived in central India in the eighth or ninth century, and especially in the eleventh, during the heyday of Nālandā and other Buddhist establishments in eastern India.

Fig. 6. Diagram identifying iconographic components of the British Museum Śaḍakṣarī Avalokiteśvara: 1. Avalokiteśvara; 2. Mañidhara; 3. Śaḍakṣarī Mahāvidyā; 4. Stūpa; 5. Buddhas; 6. Nāga figures; 7. Donors and lay followers; 8. Guardians of the Śaḍakṣarī maṇḍala.

The connection of central and eastern India, and the complexity of this later phase of Buddhism, is illustrated by a sculpture now in the collection of the British Museum. It is registered under the number Asia 1967,0213.1, and measures 82.5 cm × 54.5 cm (fig. 5). In the rest of this article, I would like to examine this sculpture in detail and present a coeval text that helps explain the place of this iconography in esoteric Buddhist practice.

Although the find-spot of the British Museum sculpture is not recorded, the style points to eastern Madhya Pradesh, as does its greenish-grey sandstone. On the basis of style it can be assigned to about the middle of the eleventh century. The iconographic elements are identified in the accompanying diagram (fig. 6). The central image is seated in *padmāsana* on a lotus; originally he had a high crown and four arms. The two hands clasped in front of his chest once held a trailing garland. The second pair of arms are missing but the hands, like the attendant deities, would have held a lotus and a rosary. Below the lotus seat are *nāgas* and kneeling donors, evidently lay followers (*upāsaka*). The main image is flanked by Mañidhara (left) and Śaḍakṣarī Mahāvidyā (right),

identifications verified, as we shall see, by the text given below. Surrounding this triad there are two cylindrical *stūpas* and five seated Buddhas. The two *stūpas* represent, I suppose, the Buddha's best known disciples, Śāriputra and Maudgalyāyana. The five Buddhas are perhaps the human or *mānuṣi* Buddhas, generally listed as Krakucchanda, Kanakamuni, Kāśyapa, Śākyamuni and Maitreya. They could also be read as the celestial or *anupapādaka* Buddhas Vairocana, Ratnasambhava, Amoghasiddhi, Amitābha and Akṣobhya. These are popularly called the "Dhyāni Buddhas," a tradition started by Brian Hodgson who was the British Resident in Nepal in the nineteenth century (Hodgson 1972: pp. 27, 54, n. 3). From there the term was taken up by E. Burnouf (Burnouf 1876: 103) and Böhtlingk and Roth (1855–1875: s.v. *dhyānibuddha*; *dhyānibodddhisattva*). On the English side, the idea was advanced by M. Monier-Williams in his Sanskrit-English Dictionary (1899: s.v. *dhyāni*). Dale E. Saunders (1962: 300–306) has charted the history of the term and noted there is no textual warrant for it. The only place it is found is in Hodgson's "Questions" in his *Essays* (Hodgson 1972: 41ff). This gives the impression of a direct quote from his informant Vajrācārya Amṛtānanda, but much paraphrasing is evident on close reading. In Amṛtānanda's *Dharmakośasaṃgraha* (Chandra 1976), prepared at Hodgson's request and now in the Asiatic Society, Calcutta, the term does not appear. In folios 15 and 16 of the text, *dhyāni* is not used where the five Buddhas are discussed but it does appear in folio 169: *ato dhyānibodhisat[t]vaḥ dhyānātsamutpānavān*. Given this, Saunders's argument is perhaps over drawn and we are obliged, I think, to note the cautious observation of Zwalf who said: "The expression has no known textual justification and is due to Brian Hodgson, British resident in Kathmandu in the early nineteenth century who may nevertheless have heard or read it" (Zwalf 1981: 60–61). Recently this problem has been revisited by Bühnemann (forthcoming).

Turning back to the British Museum sculpture, the final elements needing attention are the female figures at the extremities, top and bottom, each in *padmāsana* and each holding lotus stalks and various weapons (fig. 6). Based on the *Kāraṇḍavyūha* and the account it gives of the four guardian kings of the *ṣaḍakṣarī maṇḍala* (i.e., *maṇḍalasya*

caturdvāreṣu catvāro mahārājāḥ; Chandra 1981: folio 136), I would venture to describe the corner figures in the British Museum sculpture as the female guardians (*devakumārikā*) of the *maṇḍala*. In the lower left, curiously, there was not enough stone so the sculptor has shown the guardian with her hand on her knee and carved some sort of weapon in the pedestal.

As is often the case with later Buddhist images, the *Pratīyasamutpādagāthā* ("Verse of the origination of dependence") is inscribed on the base. The translation here follows Boucher (1991: 6). The style of the *nāgarī* characters suggests a date in the tenth or eleventh centuries C.E.

Text

1. ye dharmmā hetuprabhavā hetuḥ teṣāṃ
tathāgato hyavada
2. t | teṣāṃ yo nirodha evaṃ vādī mahāśra-
va(ma)ṇaḥ ||

Translation

Those *dharmas* that arise from a cause, the Tathāgata has declared their cause, and that which is the cessation of them. Thus the great renunciant has taught.

The identification of the British Museum image as Avalokiteśvara in the special form of *Ṣaḍakṣarī* is based on Tibetan material in which the iconography frequently occurs. A painted card in the British Museum, numbered Asia 1895,0117.0.10, shows the same deity, identified by a Tibetan inscription on the reverse as SPYAN RAS GZIGS, i.e., Avalokiteśvara. In a compendium entitled *Icons Worthy to See*, originating in an empowerment ceremony carried out in Mongolia in 1810 by the Panchen Lama, this same form is shown and labeled SPYAN RAS GZIGS YI GE DRUG PA JO BO LUGS, i.e., the six-syllabled Avalokiteśvara in the tradition of Atīśa (Willson and Brauen 2000: no. 100). The illustration shows and labels Avalokiteśvara flanked by Mañidhara and *Ṣaḍakṣarī Mahāvidyā*. The antiquity of the grouping receives textual authorization from the *sādhana* of Āryaṣaḍakṣarīmahāvidyā in the *Sāadhanamālā* that says Mañidhara should appear on the left of Lokeśvara and *Ṣaḍakṣarī Mahāvidyā* on the right. By way of conclusion, I turn now to that text.

The *Sādhanamālā* is a book of north Indian devotions in which a large number of Buddhist deities are invoked and described. The oldest copy of the text used by Benoytosh Bhattacharya for his critical edition was dated 1165 C.E. (Bhattacharya 1925–1928: xi), so we can safely assume that the *Sādhanamālā* was an active ritual text in the eleventh century and, more particularly, that the *sādhana* of Āryaśaḍakṣarīmahāvidyā can be used to explain the perception and use of the British Museum image. The only work on the *Sādhanamālā* subsequent to Bhattacharya was undertaken by Ruriko Sakuma. He prepared an edition of the Avalokiteśvara *sādhana* texts drawing on Sanskrit and Tibetan sources (Sakuma 2003). This has the advantage of giving all the relevant *sādhana*s in one place with the parallel translations in Tibetan. He did not, however, offer translations into English.

Although the critical edition of the *Sādhanamālā* was published by Bhattacharya many decades ago, there has been no attempt, as far as I am aware, to translate any of the meditations, other than the *Kiñcitvistaratārāsādhana* translated by Bhattacharya himself (Bhattacharya 1924: 169–75). Elsewhere Bhattacharya provided abstracts, but only of the portions that help explain iconographic features. In essence, art historians have drawn on the descriptions to identify the iconography of esoteric Buddhist images, but the texts as a whole, or in part, have not been studied. This sad state of affairs may be put down to the fact that while the terminology and Sanskrit are not difficult, in places the meaning and syntax are obscure. This discourages perseverance, especially as the potential result, i.e., some insight into late esoteric visualizations, has not seemed worth the effort. The increasing interest in ritual praxis, however, should bring us back to these materials. The translation offered here can be regarded as an attempt to show that the *sādhana*s are not lacking in useful data for the student of religion. Of immediate note for the art historian is the fact that although late medieval images seem to match the *sādhana* descriptions closely, there is nothing in the texts stating that images should serve as meditation aids. This is not true in eastern Asia where texts in Chinese instruct practitioners to look at images as part of the meditation process. In late medieval India, however, the texts that I have examined do not say that painted or carved images are integral to

visualization. The Indian images, therefore, seem to be commemorative memorials to those who actually undertook the practice. This is confirmed by the donor couples that appear at the base of the British Museum image (fig. 6). These figures are members of the laity, who were inspired to make the image in order to celebrate the visualization and generate merit. In other words, the donor figures shown in the sculpture provide a visual link to the inscription on the Raisen pedestal where the name of the donor is actually given. The wider social world of these images and the people named or pictured in them are a subject with much potential. The *Upāsakajanāṅkara*, a handbook for the Buddhist laity written in south India in the second half of the twelfth century C.E., could be taken as a starting point. It was composed to supersede the *Paṭipattisaṅgha*, a work that exists only in manuscript in Japan (Hinüber 1996: § 386). North Indian material in Sanskrit is also available (Agostini 2003). Outside the Buddhist fold, analogous material makes up the *Śivadharmaśāstra*, a corpus that sets out the religious obligations and ritual activities of lay followers of Śiva. Apart from the recent and somewhat flawed survey by Paolo Magone (2004), these works are effectively unstudied. Taken with the Buddhist texts, this material offers an historical sociology beyond the monasteries and royal courts of the medieval world.

To close this essay, I give the text and translation of the Āryaśaḍakṣarīmahāvidyā *sādhana*. This is presented in an interlinear fashion so the meaning of the text, or at least my understanding of it, can be directly compared to the original (the text given here appears in Bhattacharya's *Sādhanamālā* as number 6). I would like to thank Whitney Cox and Mattia Salvini for the helpful suggestions on the text and its translation.

āryaśaḍakṣarīmahāvidyāyai namaḥ

“Obeisance to the noble Śaḍakṣarī Mahāvidyā”

ādau tāvan mantrī sukhāsanopaviṣṭaḥ mukhaśaucādikam kṛtvā svahṛdi candrasthasitahrīḥkāravinirgataśmibhir gurubuddhabodhisattvān purato buddhādīn dṛṣṭvā sampūjyatriśaraṇagamanādikam kuryād ratnatrayaṃ me śaraṇam ity ādinā ||

“To begin, the *mantra*-practioner, sitting comfortably, cleanses his mouth and so forth and

then, in his heart, visualizes the Buddha [Dharma and Saṅgha] in the presence of the Buddhas, the Bodhisattvas and his guru by means of rays issuing from the white syllable HRĪḤ set in the moon. He should then perform the going to refuge in the respected triple gem and the rest by saying: "The three jewels are my refuge, etc'."

yāvantaḥ sattvāḥ sattvasaṃgrahaṇa saṃgrhitāḥ aṇḍajā vā jarāyujā vā saṃsvedaḥ vā aupapādukā vā rūpiṇo vā arūpiṇo vā saṃjñino vā asaṃjñino vā naivasamjñānāsamjñino vā yāvān kaścit sattvadhātuḥ prajñāpyamānaḥ prajñāpyate sarve mayā anupadhiśeṣanirvāṇadhātau pratiṣṭhāpayitavyā iti ||

[And pronouncing the Bodhisattva vow]:⁴ "Whatever beings (*yāvantaḥ sattvāḥ*) are included (*saṃgrhitāḥ*) in the totality of existence (*sattvasaṃgrahaṇa*), whether born from eggs, wombs (*jarāyujā*), sweat or self-generated (*aupapādukā*), whether corporeal or non-corporeal, conscious, unconscious or neither conscious nor unconscious, and whatever other domain of life that is known to be known (*sattvadhātuḥ prajñāpyamānaḥ prajñāpyate*), by me all of them shall be established in the domain of *nirvāṇa* without a remainder."

tataḥ oṃ svabhāvaśuddhāḥ sarvadharmāḥ svabhāvaśuddho 'haṃ iti vāratrayam uccārayet |

"Then he should pronounce thrice as follows: 'OM all phenomena are pure by nature, I am pure by nature'."

tadanu śūnyatām muhūrtam ālambayet |

"Afterward, for a moment, he should take emptiness (*śūnyatā*) as his point of reference."

tad anantaram svahṛdaye sitapadmopari candramaṇḍalaṃ tasyopari sitahrīḥ kāraṃ tato niścarad anekaraśmīsatasaḥasraṃ dhyātvā, tena sarvasattvānām aśeṣānādikālasaṅcītaṃ rāgādi kleśasamūhaṃ viśodhyante |

"Thereupon, he meditates on a lunar circle set on top of a white lotus in his own heart and, on top of that, the white syllable HRĪḤ emanating uncounted thousands of rays. That purifies the aggregate afflictions of all sentient beings, such

as passion, that have been accumulated from eternity."

tat punas tatraiva praveśayet |

"Afterward he should make (the syllable) return right there (to his heart)."⁵

tat pariṇatam ātmānaṃ lokeśvararūpam sarvā-lāṅkārabhūṣitaṃ śuklavarnaṃ caturbhujam vāmataḥ padmadharam, dakṣiṇato akṣasūtradharam, aparābhyāṃ hastābhyāṃ hr̥ḍi saṃpuṭāñjalishtitaṃ dhyāyāt |

"Then he should meditate on himself transformed in the form of Lokeśvara, white of color, ornamented with every decoration, four armed, on the left holding a lotus, on the right holding a rosary, the lower two hands cupped in front of the heart;"

dakṣiṇe maṇidharam tadvarṇabhujānvitam padmāntaropariṣṭham vāme tataivāparapadmasthām ṣaḍakṣarīmahāvidyām |

"On the right, seated on a lotus, Maṇidhara, of similar color and (number of) arms; on the left, seated on a lotus in the exact same manner, Ṣaḍakarī Mahāvidyā."

tataḥ oṃ mahāsukha vajrasattva jaḥ huṃ vaṃ hoḥ suratas tvam alalalala hoḥ aḥ aḥ aḥ aḥ ity adhiṣṭhānamantrarājam uccārayet |

"Then he should pronounce the king of empowerment *mantras*: MAHĀSUKHA VAJRASATTVA JAḤ HUM VAṃ HOḤ SURATAS TVAM ALALALALALA HOḤ AḤ AḤ AḤ AḤ."

evaṃ dhyātvā tato lokeśvarātmahṛdayacandramaṇḍalād akṣasūtrākāraṃ śuklavarnaṃ mukhena nirgatya nābhau praviśantaṃ cakrabhramaṇayogena imaṃ mantrarājam sarvabuddhahṛdayacīntāmaṇikalpaṃ paśyed animittayogena |

"Having meditated so, he should then visualize this king of *mantras* in the form of a rosary, white in color, coming out of his mouth from the lunar circle set in the heart of Lokeśvara himself and entering [his] navel in the manner of a rotating wheel. And he should see, in a manner that is empty, the king of *mantras* as a wishing-fulfilling stone in the heart of all the Buddhas."

tato japaṃ kṛtvā⁶ bhramaṇapraveśanādikaṃ
prāpyācireṇaiva kālena śrāddhaḥ kṛpāvān guru-
bhakto yogī sidhyati | oṃ maṇipadme hūṃ iti
jāpamantraḥ ||

“Then performing a *japa*, having achieved the [aforementioned] rotating and entering [of the *mantra*] etc., the yogī, compassionate, faithful and devoted to his guru, succeeds in a truly short time. The *japa mantra* is: Oṃ MAṆI PAME HŪM.”

tata utthānakāle imaṃ mantrarājam uccāryot-
tiṣṭhet |

“Then, when it is time to get up (from medita-
tion), having spoken this king of *mantras*, he
should rise saying:”

oṃ vajrasattva samayam anupālaya vajrasattva-
tvenopatiṣṭha, dṛḍho me bhava, sutoṣyo me
bhava, supoṣyo me bhava, anurakto me bhava,
sarvasiddhiṃ me prayaccha, sarvakarmasu ca me
cittaṃ śreyaḥ kuru huṃ ha ha ha ha hoḥ bhaga-
van sarvatathāgatavajra mā me muñca, vajribhava
mahāsamayasattva āḥ |

“Oṃ Vajrasattva! Preserve the pledge! Be present
as Vajrasattva! Be steadfast for me! Be content in
me! Be fulfilled for me! Be loving to me! Bestow
all powers on me! Make my thought better in all
deeds! HUṃ HA HA HA HA HOḥ. Lord! Vajra of
all the Tathāgatas, abandon me not! Be the bearer
of the immutable, oh being of the great pledge!
Āḥ.”

evam uktvā yathāsukhaṃ vihared iti |

“Having spoken thus, let him go at his pleasure.”

āryaśaḍakṣarīmahāvidyāsādhanam samāptam |

“The *sādhana* of Mahāvidyā of the noble Ārya-
śaḍakṣarī is concluded.”

Notes

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1. () = uncertain readings
{ } = illegible text supplied conjecturally
[] = omitted akṣaras supplied conjecturally
2. Expressed as a symbol.
3. The *anusvāra* is placed after the letters, not above the line; possibly read name as Vaṭṭāṃka.
4. This Bodhisattva vow is quoted directly from the *Vajracchedikā Prajñāpāramitā Sūtra* 3 (Vaidya 1961: 3).
5. In other words, when the syllable with its many rays goes out and purifies all sentient beings, it should thereafter return to the practitioner’s heart. This understanding is based on the parallel in one of the Tibetan translations: YI GE DE NYID RANG GI SNYING GAR BCUG PAS, “that syllable he should insert in his own heart.”
6. The syntax does not seem to be completely logical; the Tibetan translations do not transmit the words *japaṃ kṛtvā*, suggesting this insertion took place after the text was transmitted.

References

- Agostini 2003 G. Agostini. “On the Nikāya Affiliation of the Śrīghānācārasaṅgraha and the Sphuṭārthā Śrīghānācārasaṅgrahaṭīkā.” *JIAS* 26.1: 97–114.
- Amar 2012 A. S. Amar. “Buddhist Responses to Brāhmaṇa Challenges in Medieval India: Bodhgayā and Gayā.” *JRAS* 22.1: 155–85.
- Bhattacharya 1924 B. Bhattacharya. *Indian Buddhist Iconography*. Oxford.
- Bhattacharya 1925–1928 ———. Ed. *Sādhanamālā*. 2 vols. Baroda.
- Böhtlingk and Roth 1855–1875 O. von Böhtlingk and G. Roth. *Sanskrit Wörterbuch*. 7 vols. Saint Petersburg.
- Boucher 1991 D. Boucher. “The Pratītyasamutpādagāthā and Its Role in the Medieval Cult of Relics.” *JIAS* 14: 1–27.
- Bronkhorst 2012 J. Bronkhorst. *Buddhism in the Shadow of Brahmanism*. Leiden.
- Burnouf 1876 E. Burnouf. *Introduction à l’histoire du Bouddhisme indien*. 2nd ed. Paris.
- Bühnemann forthcoming G. Bühnemann. “A *dhāraṇī* for Each Day of the Week: The *saptavāra* Tradition of the Newar Buddhists.” *BSOAS*.

- Chandra 1976 L. Chandra. *Dharmakośa-saṃgraha: Facsimile with Introduction*. Delhi.
- Chandra 1981 _____ . *Kāraṇḍavyūha and Other Texts*. Delhi.
- Cousins 2003 L. C. Cousins. "Śākiya-bhikkhu/Sakyabhikkhu/Śākyabhikṣu: A Mistaken Link to the Mahāyāna?" *Sam̐bhāṣā—Nagoya Studies in Indian Culture and Buddhism* 23: 1–27.
- Desai 1996 D. Desai. *The Religious Imagery of Khajuraho*. Mumbai.
- Dikshit 1921 K. N. Dikshit. *Six Sculptures from Mahoba*. Memoirs of the Archaeological Survey of India, vol. 8. Calcutta.
- Gethin 2012 R. Gethin. "Was Buddhaghosa a Theravādin? Buddhist Identity in the Pali Commentaries and Chronicles." In *How Theravāda is Theravāda?: Exploring Buddhist Identities*, ed. P. Skilling et al., 1–63. Bangkok.
- Hamid et al. 1922 M. M. Hamid et al. *Catalogue of the Museum of Archaeology at Sanchi, Bhopal State*. Calcutta.
- Hinüber 1996 O. von Hinüber. *A Handbook of Pali Literature*. Berlin.
- Hodgson 1972 B. Hodgson. *Essays on the Language, Literature and Religion of Nepal and Tibet*. Calcutta, 1875; repr. with supplement, Amsterdam, 1972.
- Magone 2004 P. Magone. "Śivadharmottara: Spigolature da un tardo upapurāṇa settario." In *Atti dell'Undicesimo Convegno Nazionale di Studi Sanscriti* (Milano, 22–23 novembre 2002), 115–28. Turin.
- Monier-Williams 1889 M. Monier-Williams. *Buddhism in Its Connection with Brāhmanism and Hindūism, and Its Connection with Christianity*. 2nd ed. New York.
- Monier-Williams 1899 _____ . *Sanskrit-English Dictionary*. Oxford.
- Sakuma 2003 R. Sakuma. *Sādhanamālā, Avalokiteśvara Section: Sanskrit and Tibetan Texts*. New Delhi.
- Sanderson 2009 A. Sanderson. "The Śaiva Age—The Rise and Dominance of Śaivism during the Early Medieval Period." In *Genesis and Development of Tantrism*, ed. E. Shingo, 41–349. Tokyo.
- Saunders 1962 D. E. Saunders. "A Note on Śakti and Dhyānibuddha." *History of Religions* 1: 300–306.
- Schopen 2005 G. Schopen. *Figments and Fragments of Mahāyāna Buddhism in India: More Collected Papers*. Honolulu.
- Tsukamoto 1996 K. Tsukamoto. *A Comprehensive Study of the Indian Buddhist Inscriptions*. 2 pts. Kyoto.
- Vaidya 1961 P. L. Vaidya. *Mahāyāna-sūtra-saṃgrahaḥ (part 1)*. Darbhanga.
- Willis 1996 M. Willis. *Inscriptions of Gopaksetra: Materials for the History of Central India*. London.
- Willis 1999–2000 _____ . "The Sanchi Bodhi-sattva Dated Kuṣāṇa Year 28." *Silk Road Art and Archaeology* 6: 269–73.
- Willis 2000 _____ . *Buddhist Reliquaries from Ancient India*. London.
- Willis 2001 _____ . "Buddhist Saints in Ancient Vedisa." *JRAS* 11: 219–28.
- Willis 2013 _____ . "From World Religion to World Dominion: Trading, Translation and Institution-building in Tibet." In *Trading Religions: Religious Formation, Transformation and Cross-Cultural Exchange between East and West*, ed. P. Wick and V. Rabens, 141–57. Leiden.
- Willson and Brauen 2000 M. Willson and M. Brauen, eds. *Deities of the Tibetan Buddhism*. Boston.
- Zwalf 1981 W. Zwalf. *Heritage of Tibet*. London.

